
Project Title	SCAlable LAttice Boltzmann Leaps to Exascale
Project Acronym	SCALABLE
Grant Agreement No.	956000
Start Date of Project	01.01.2021
Duration of Project	36 Months
Project Website	www.scalable-hpc.eu

D6.3

Best practice guide for next-gen industrial systems for large scale CFD simulations based on LB methods

Work Package	WP 6: Development and Deployment Platforms and Services
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Due Date	31.12.2023
Date	10.01.2024
Version	0.9

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

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The Scalable project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 956000.

Deliverable Information

Deliverable	D6.3
Deliverable Type	
Deliverable Title	Best practice guide for next-gen industrial systems for large scale CFD simulations based on LB methods
Keywords	recommended system architecture, CFD, LBM, hardware architecture
Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package	WP 6: Development and Deployment Platforms and Services
Lead Partner	IT4I
Lead Author	L. Riha
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Reviewed By	Romain CUIDARD (CSGROUP), Corentin LEFEVRE (Neovia)
Due Date	31.12.2023
Planned Date	10.1.2024
Version	0.9
Final Version Date	10.01.2024

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Best practice guide for next-gen industrial systems for large scale CFD simulations based on LB methods

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January 10, 2024

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Part 1.

Next-gen industrial systems for large-scale CFD simulations based on LB methods

A. Optimal HPC architecture for SCALABLE codes

Based on the experience gathered from performance evaluation of SCALABLE codes on different hardware platforms in WP2, WP4 and WP6, this deliverable defines the optimal architecture of the HPC system for LBM based codes. First, we evaluated the performance of both LaBS and waLBerla on accessible hardware platforms to project partners. In case of LaBS only CPU platforms are of interest as GPU version is in early development stage. The GPU recommendations are purely based on waLBerla measurements as its implementation is mature and because the code generation technique that generates the GPU kernels is also ported to LaBS.

A.1. CPU Architecture Recommendations

This section focuses on an analysis of the behavior of both codes on different processor architectures to extrapolate the behavior for different processor parameters. In general, from the WP2 and WP4 deliverables, both LaBS and waLBerla are memory bound codes, and one of the critical parameters is the memory bandwidth per CPU core. The evolution of this parameter for different generations of AMD and Intel processors is shown in Figure 1 (Credits: John McCaplin, Link: <https://sites.utexas.edu/jdm4372/2023/04/25/the-evolution-of-single-core-bandwidth-in-multicore-processors/>). The figure clearly shows that today's AMD processors have a higher per-core memory bandwidth.

Figure 1: The evolution of single-core bandwidth in multicore processors. Credits: John McCaplin

Another important property we observed from the WP2 deliverables is that the total memory bandwidth achieved by the SCALABLE codes for different numbers of cores is different from the purely memory-bound STREAM benchmark. On AMD chiplet-based CPUs the STREAM benchmarks need only 1 active core per memory channel/chiplet to reach maximum memory bandwidth. For such a workload, one does not need large core count per processor.

However, this is not the case for SCALABLE codes. As shown in Figure 2 measured memory bandwidth per node (with two 64-core CPUs) scales with the number of cores up to 128 cores. The increase in memory

LaBS 2.6 DRT scheme Lagoon 470^3 cells 512 timesteps on 2 nodes of Karolina

Figure 2: LABS original Lagoon DRAM bandwidth vs MLups on 2 nodes.

bandwidth also translates into growth in performance in MLups per node. So, from this point of view, using high core count SKUs brings extra performance.

For LaBS we focus only on the CPU-based clusters, as production version is CPU only without accelerator support. For waLBerla we evaluate performance on both CPUs and GPU accelerators to define GPU recommendations.

For this section, we used the Lagoon test case (see D2.1 for detailed use case description) of size that fits into a single node memory because most platforms used for performance evaluation are available only as single servers. The scalability of both codes is presented in public deliverables D2.3 and D2.4.

A.2. HBM performance on Sapphire Rapids CPUs

The paper published at [1] evaluates the performance of the memory subsystem featuring High Bandwidth Memory (HBM) of the Intel Xeon Max 9480 processor using two 2-socket system. Systems have identical processors and motherboards, with one system configured to use only DDR5 memory (HBM disabled by BIOS) and the other configured to use only HBM memory (DDR5 DIMMs physically removed). Both systems were configured with Rocky Linux 8.6.

The key conclusion provided in the paper is the limited real memory bandwidth when compared to the theoretical (peak) performance of the installed HBM interfaces. The summary of findings is in the Table1 which shows that the HBM version has 3.5x higher bandwidth (700 GB/s for HBM vs. 200 GB/s for DDR5 - both for a single socket) but it only reaches 42% of the peak performance.

In the Table1, we have also added STREAM results for AMD Genoa CPU (EPYC 9654) with 12 DDR interfaces. Compared to this CPU the HBM version of Xeon Max 9480 reached only 2x higher memory bandwidth. Another option to reach higher memory bandwidth is to use LPDDR5 memories as it is the case of NVidia Grace. This solution is estimated to bring about approximately 10% higher bandwidth compared to the AMD Genoa.

If interested, the paper describes what are the main reasons of the limited performance in greater detail, but for purpose of this deliverable we can summarize that this is the maximum bandwidth user application can achieve.

A.3. Optimal CPU for LaBS

Since the current production version of LaBS is CPU only, we have evaluated the different CPU technologies currently available. We present an evaluation of 3 AMD platforms and 2 most recent Intel platforms, Ice Lake, and Sapphire Rapids with HBM memory. We used LaBS version and benchmark from Table 2.

We have compared the performance of LaBS on different AMD and Intel processors in Table 3. To further support the argument about the number of cores, the table also shows the performance when only one-half or one-quarter of CPU cores are used.

Focusing on AMD processors based on Zen3 architecture. We have three SKUs in the table. The 7763 is a very common SKU for HPC systems with 64 cores (maximum for Zen3 core generation), and in general it

Processor	DDR5 interfaces	HBM interfaces	Peak performance	STREAM Triad (%Peak)
Xeon Platinum 8480+ (56 cores, 2.0 GHz)	8x 64-bit @ 4.8 GT/s	N/A	307.2 GB/s	200 GB/s (65.1%)
Xeon Max 9480 DDR5 (56 cores, 1.9 GHz)	8x 64-bit @ 4.8 GT/s	(disabled)	307.2 GB/s	201 GB/s (65.4%)
Xeon Max 9480 HBM (56 cores, 1.9 GHz)	(Not installed)	4x 1024-bit @ 3.2 GT/s	1638.4 GB/s	700 GB/s (42.7%)
AMD EPYC 7763	8x 64-bit @ 3.2 GT/s	N/A	204.8 GB/s	168 GB/s (78.1%)
AMD EPYC 9654	12x 64-bit @ 4.8 GT/s	N/A	460.8 GB/s	350 GB/s (76.0%)
NVidia Grace chip 72 cores	LPDDR5x	N/A	500 GB/s expected	400 - 450 GB/s expected

Table 1: Comparison of the DDR5 and HBM memory theoretical and real performance on the Intel Sapphire Rapids generation CPUs with other architectures. The results are measured for single socket on the dual socket server.

Code	Version used for benchmarking	use-case	Platform
LaBS	3.1	Lagoon small version	CPU only

Table 2: Software version and benchmark specification for LaBS

would be a natural choice for general-purpose HPC systems like the ones installed in national supercomputing centers. If we compare its performance to the AMD 7773X which is an SKU enhanced with large L3 cache of 768MB, we clearly see that the benefit of the large L3 cache is negligible, and there is no benefit to pay an additional \$1000 (launch prize) for this feature.

Returning to the AMD 7763 we also see performance improvements from the previous generation (Zen2 based 7H12 SKU) approximately from 68 MLups and 1.06 MLups per core (7H12) to 88 MLups and 1.38 MLups per core (7763), resulting in an approximately 30% performance increase. Therefore, one can expect to see a non-negligible performance increase also moving to Zen4 architecture. This expected increase in performance will also be supported by almost double memory bandwidth, see Table 1.

Processor	Key properties	All cores	1/2 cores	1/4 cores
AMD 7H12 (Zen2)	64 cores, DDR4 280W TDP	652.6 s 68.36 MLUPs	819.8 s 54.42 MLUPs	1218.6 s 36.61 MLUPs
AMD 7763 (Zen3)	64 cores, DDR4 280W TDP	503.2 s 88.65 MLUPs	657.6 s 67.85 MLUPs	1071.1 s 41.65 MLUPs
AMD 7513 (Zen3)	32 cores, DDR4 200W TDP	699.2 s 63.81 MLUPs	1033.5 s 43.17 MLUPs	1864.4 s 23.93 MLUPs
AMD 7773X (Zen3)	64 cores, 768 MB L3 280W TDP	502.4 s 88.79 MLUPs	661.2 s 67.47 MLUPs	1065.9 s 41.85 MLUPs
Intel Xeon 6338 (Ice Lake)	32 cores, DDR4 185 TDP	715.3 s 62.37 MLUPs	1048.0 s 42.57 MLUPs	1956.4 s 22.80 MLUPs
Intel Xeon Max 9468 (Sapphire Rapids)	48 cores, HBM + DDR5 350W TDP	382.9 s 116 MLUPs	620.5 s 71.90 MLUPs	1083.2 s 41.69 MLUPs

Table 3: Performance evaluation of the LaBS using Lagoon benchmark for different CPU architectures

A similar hardware evaluation has been done for two recent Intel CPU architectures (IceLake and Sapphire Rapids). In particular, the Sapphire Rapids CPU generation, represented here by a 48-core Intel Xeon Max 9468, is the first x86 CPU with High Bandwidth Memory. LaBS being memory-bound is able to take advantage of this fast memory and achieved the highest performance of 116 MLups per node (2.41 MLups per core). This is approximately 2x speedup when compared to the previous Intel Ice Lake generation with 32 cores, 62.4 MLups (1.95 MLups per core).

In general, we can state that the per-core performance is the best for Intel Sapphire Rapids CPU with HBM memory. Per socket/node level, this system also delivers maximum performance of all tested platforms. But we also have to take into account that the Sapphire Rapids release date was January 10, 2023, while the AMD Milan release date was March 15, 2021. A more relevant comparison would be with AMD Genoa, which release date was November 10, 2022. As of now, we do not have access to any AMD Genoa server, therefore we only

present it with basic information for basic comparison in Table 1.

The presented results are for 48 core SKU (Intel Xeon Max 9468); however, there are also 56 core SKUs with HBM memory (9480). Since the HBM memory bandwidth scales with the number of cores within the entire range, one can expect a performance increase close to 135 MLups. However, the list price for this SKU is \$12980.

Zen4 is expected to have the similar performance per core as Zen3, however, the number of cores grows from 64 to 96, theoretically resulting in up to 50% extra performance. In our case, this performance increase will also be supported by the extra memory bandwidth.

A basic estimate of performance for Genoa 9654 with 96 cores and 350 GB/s of STREAM triad bandwidth can be done based on Milan 7763 performance. When we compare these two, the Zen4 generation has the following advantages:

1. approx. 34% higher per core bandwidth (3.6 GB/s vs. 2.6 GB/s),
2. approx. 2x per chip memory bandwidth in STREAM Triad benchmark,
3. 1.5x number of CPU cores,
4. approx. 30% higher performance when comparing Zen2 (7H12) and Zen3 (7763) with the same number of cores and the same memory interface.

Taking all this into account, one can expect the LaBS performance to be in the range 130 (by CPU core scaling) and 180 (memory bandwidth scaling) MLUPS, which puts this CPU in direct comparison with the top-of-the-line Intel Xeon Max SKUs (like 9468). The competitiveness also holds in the price of the two CPUs as AMD 9954 and Intel Xeon Max 9467 cost \$11,805 and \$12,980, respectively.

A.3.1. Recommendations

The final summary of the compared HW platforms is presented in Table 4. Since LaBS does not linearly scale to all CPU cores on high-core-count SKUs, the most optimal solution is to focus on SKUs with lower-core-count SKUs. These SKUs, represented by AMD 7515 and Intel 6338, both have low launch price and their performance per cost is 2x better compared to the 64-core AMD 7763. We have selected the reference processor, AMD 7763 as it is widely used in general purpose HPC systems installed in the past few years in EuroHPC systems. Then we calculate the relative performance per Watt and performance per cost wrt. to this processor.

Processor	Key properties	Time [s] Perf. [MLups]	TDP [W] Launch price [\$]	Mlups/W Mlups/\$	Relative to AMD 7763 Mlups/W Mlups/\$
AMD 7H12 (Zen2)	64 cores, DDR4	652,6	280	0,122	77%
		68,36	7300	0,00468	83%
AMD 7763 (Zen3)	64 cores, DDR4	503,2	280	0,158	100%
		88,65	7890	0,00562	100%
AMD 7513 (Zen3)	32 cores, DDR4	699,2	200	0,160	101%
		63,81	2840	0,01123	200%
AMD 7773X (Zen3)	64 cores, 768 MB L3	502,4	280	0,159	100%
		88,79	8800	0,00504	90%
Intel Xeon 6338 (Ice Lake)	32 cores, DDR4	715,3	185	0,169	106%
		62,37	2612	0,01194	213%
Intel Xeon Max 9468 (Sapphire Rapids)	48 cores, HBM + DDR5	382,9	350	0,166	105%
		116	9900	0,00586	104%
AMD 9654 (Zen4)	96 cores, DDR5	–	400	0,163	103%
		130*	11805	0,00551	98%
AMD 9654 (Zen4)	96 cores, DDR5	–	400	0,225	142%
		180**	11805	0,00762	136%
AMD 9334 (Zen4)	32 cores, DDR5	–	210	0,217	137%
		91*	2999	0,01517	270%
AMD 9334 (Zen4)	32 cores, DDR5	–	210	0,300	190%
		126**	2999	0,02101	374%

Table 4: LaBS (For Genoa: * - expected lower bound, ** - expected upper bound)

Although the Intel MAX 9464 provided the best time-to-solution, due to its high TDP of 350W and high price, it provides similar energy efficiency and performance per cost as the older high-end AMD Zen3 based CPUs like AMD 7763.

The energy efficiency of all CPUs is comparable, and there is no significant gain in selecting one or another. The significant improvement in energy efficiency should be achieved by AMD Genoa CPUs. We were unable to run LaBS on this new architecture, but from its key parameters we have estimated the lower and upper performance to provide basic guidelines. Based on these, when AMD 9334 with 32 cores is used, one can see up to 50% better energy efficiency.

As such, our main advice for procurement is to focus on the AMD Genoa CPUs and in particular the low-core-count versions (for instance, AMD 9334), which still have the same memory bandwidth as the high-end ones like AMD 9654 maintaining high efficiency with comparable performance for a fraction of cost.

A.4. Optimal CPU for waLBerla

The current version of WaLBerla is fully ported for GPU accelerators, and as such a GPU-accelerated cluster is the recommended choice. However, for companies that want to build a CPU-based cluster because they plan to use both LaBS and waLBerla we have also performed the same performance evaluation for the same CPU architectures as in the case of LaBS, see Table 6 for results and Table 5 for use case identification. Again, the use-case description is in D2.1.

Code	Version used for benchmarking	use-case	Platform
waLBerla	33af3994223b6cf3e31f28b5c0022908b9e0a553	Lagoon small version	CPU
waLBerla	33af3994223b6cf3e31f28b5c0022908b9e0a553	Lagoon GPU version	GPU

Table 5: Software and benchmark specification for ProLB

The first key observation is that waLBerla scales with much better efficiency in high-core-count SKUs. However, the AMD 7515 SKU with 32 cores still reaches almost 78% of the 64-core AMD 7763 performance. This is achieved with 72% of the power budget (based on the TDP) and, most importantly, with 36% of the price per CPU (based on launch prize).

The Intel 6338 CPU, however, for waLBerla is not as suitable as for LaBS both in energy efficiency as well as performance price. This is caused by the low performance of the older IceLake cores. Also, the Intel Max 9468 with HBM memory does not provide convincing results as its performance is similar to the older AMD 7763, but at a cost of higher TDP.

Processor	Key properties	All cores	1/2 cores	1/4 cores
AMD 7H12 (Zen2)	64 cores, DDR4	305.7 [s]	488 [s]	939.2 [s]
		219.1 [MLUPs]	137.1 [MLUPs]	71.3 [MLUPs]
AMD 7763 (Zen3)	64 cores, DDR4	255.5 [s]	500.7 [s]	967.6 [s]
		262.1 [MLUPs]	133 [MLUPs]	68.7 [MLUPs]
AMD 7513 (Zen3)	32 cores, DDR4	326.52 [s]	624.74 [s]	1151.8 [s]
AMD 7773X (Zen3)	64 cores, 768 MB L3	205.123 [MLUPs]	107.207 [MLUPs]	58.1495 [MLUPs]
		309.618 [s]	304.605 [s]	352.032 [s]
Intel Xeon 6338 (Ice Lake)	32 cores, DDR4	216.32 [MLUPs]	219.88 [MLUPs]	190.257 [MLUPs]
		94.1086 [MLUPs]	68.651 [MLUPs]	39.3394 [MLUPs]
Intel Xeon Max 9468 (Sapphire Rapids)	48 cores, DDR5 + HBM	711.694 [s]	975.608 [s]	1702.53 [s]
		271.551 [s]	367.48 [s]	907.54 [s]
		246.644 [MLUPs]	182.259 [MLUPs]	73.80 [MLUPs]

Table 6: Performance evaluation of the waLBerla using Lagoon benchmark for different CPU architectures

A.4.1. Recommendations

As in the case of LaBS we have summarized waLBerla performance results, power consumption, and CPU cost in Table 7. The best time to solution is achieved by the 64-core AMD 7763. If performance per price is the key indicator, the best solution is the 32-core AMD 7515, which has a 2.2x higher MLups/\$ ratio.

Energy efficiency in all compared CPUs is in close proximity. Both Intel CPUs have the lowest numbers. Based on expected results for Genoa processor, we can see that energy efficiency should be significantly improved together with performance per price.

We definitely recommend considering these new CPUs and in particular the lower core count, here represented by AMD 9334. The high core count SKUs are compatible only for faster time-to-solution.

However, waLberla being fully ported to both Nvidia and AMD GPUs can provide even higher performance, as shown in the next section.

Processor	Key properties	Time [s] Perf. [Mlups]	TDP [W] Launch price [\$]	Mlups/W Mlups/\$	Relative to AMD 7763
					Mlups/W Mlups/\$
AMD 7H12 (Zen2)	64 cores, DDR4	305,7 219,1	280 7300	0,391 0,01501	84% 90%
AMD 7763 (Zen3)	64 cores, DDR4	255,5 262,1	280 7890	0,468 0,01661	100% 100%
AMD 7513 (Zen3)	32 cores, DDR4	326,5 205,1	200 2840	0,513 0,03611	110% 217%
AMD 7773X (Zen3)	64 cores, 768 MB L3	309,6 216,3	280 8800	0,386 0,01229	83% 74%
Intel Xeon 6338 (Ice Lake)	32 cores, DDR4	711,7 94,10	185 2612	0,254 0,01801	54% 108%
Intel Xeon Max 9468 (Sapphire Rapids)	48 cores, DDR5 + HBM	271,5 246,6	350 9900	0,352 0,01246	75% 75%
AMD 9654 (Zen4)	96 cores, DDR5	390*	400 11805	0,488 0,01652	104% 99%
AMD 9654 (Zen4)	96 cores, DDR5	530**	400 11805	0,663 0,02245	142% 135%
AMD 9334 (Zen4)	32 cores, DDR5	273*	210 2999	0,650 0,04552	139% 274%
AMD 9334 (Zen4)	32 cores, DDR5	371**	210 2999	0,883 0,06185	189% 372%

Table 7: waLberla (For Genoa: * - expected lower bound, ** - expected upper bound)

A.5. GPU recommendations

The GPU evaluation is based on waLberla as it allows us to compare two main vendors of the GPU accelerators, Nvidia and AMD. We have evaluated the Nvidia A100 in two configurations. The first is the most common combination of 4 GPUs per node that are connected peer-to-peer using NVLink interconnect but providing limited bandwidth among GPUs. The second configuration uses 8x A100 GPUs per node and all GPUs are interconnected using NVswitch, which allows maximum bandwidth between any pair of GPUs in a server.

The Lagoon use case uses the adaptive mesh refinement for both CPU and GPU versions, and therefore the performance is limited when compared to the version with AMR. The performance limit is caused by the GPU-aware communications. This is also the reason why 4 GPUs per node achieve better performance than 8 GPUs per node. Finally, the last GPU accelerator evaluated is the AMD MI250X installed in the LUMI-G supercomputer. The performance results for all GPU accelerators is presented in Table 8.

	Key properties	Time and performance
Nvidia A100 4 GPUs w/o NVSwitch	4x 40GB HBM2 FZJ Booster	0.47 time [s] 3662.46 [MLUPs]
Nvidia A100 8 GPUs w. NVSwitch	8x 40GB HBM2 IT4I Karolina	0.32 time [s] 5308.75 [MLUPs]
AMD MI250X 4 GPUs (8 virtual)	4x 128GB HBM2e LUMI-G system	0.499 time [s] 3454,3 [MLUPs]

Table 8: Performance and energy efficiency evaluation of the benchmark for different GPU architectures running waLberla

We have evaluated the same metrics as for the CPUs also for these three GPUs in Table 9. Unfortunately, the cost of GPUs is not generally available like a launch price for CPUs. Therefore, based on search of several integrators, customization systems we derived the cost is approximately the same for both A100 with 40GB memory and MI250X, &15,000.

GPU	Time Mlups	MLups per /GPU	TDP [W] Launch price [\$]	Mlups/W Mlups/\$	related to 4x A100 Mlups/W Mlups/\$	related to AMD 7513 Mlups/W Mlups/\$	related to AMD 9334 Mlups/W Mlups/\$
Nvidia A100 4 GPUs w/o NVSwitch	0,47 3662,4	915,6	400 15000	2,289 0,061	100% 100%	4,46 1,69	3,52* 1,34*
Nvidia A100 8 GPUs w, NVSwitch	0,32 5308,7	663,6	400 15000	1,659 0,044	72% 72%	3,24 1,23	2,55* 0,97*
AMD MI250X 4 GPUs (8 virtual)	0,499 3454,3	863,6	500 15000	1,727 0,058	75% 94%	3,37 1,59	2,66* 1,26*

Table 9: waLBerla on GPU (For Genoa: * - estimated performance)

From a performance point of view, the 4x A100 has almost identical performance as the 4xMI250x. However, in case of AMD, one MI250X is actually a dual-chiplet GPU. This also affects the performance due to AMR enabled in the use case. The MI250X has significantly higher memory bandwidth and peak performance; see Table 10, but waLBerla cannot take advantage of this. Also, this comes at a cost of higher TDP which yields lower energy efficiency.

In terms of performance per cost, the MI250X and A100 are giving similar results, which in general is very good open competition in the tender. There are also newly released GPUs that we were unable to evaluate. The NVidia H100, AMD MI300X, and MI300A are bringing the new level of performance to HPC systems, and during the procurement, these should be also considered. We present them in the final section of this deliverable.

Finally, to close the story, we have compared the GPUs with the CPUs. When we take current generations (AMD Zen3 - 7513, Nvidia A100 and MI250X) we can see that energy efficiency is approximately 3.5 times higher in favor of GPUs. More interesting is the performance per price ratio. We can see that AMD 7513 is only 1,7 times worse and the new Genoa-based AMD 9334 is only 1,34 times worse than NVidia A100.

However, this is only the OPEX cost for procuring the system. Since these days when a significant part of CAPEX is electricity, GPU systems cut this cost significantly and therefore should be the first for waLBerla-only clusters.

B. Best-practice guide for system procurement

B.1. Procurement guide

Procurement conditions and reference vary between centers. This section will provide a basic view of what to include in a procurement proposition.

Summarized requirements for the procurement document:

- Objective of the procurement: Replacement of a previous system? Is it Targeting a specific computing metric (raw performance, simulation throughput, access to a new architecture)?
- Cost range.
- Timeframe for the propositions and delivery date.
- Timeframe for the life cycle of the new system.
- Additional conditions: targeted energy efficiency, preferred architectures if any, preferred components if any (network, storage, etc.).

The basic conditions for a procurement document to be acceptable by a vendor are the available funding and the targeted metric for the new system. These guarantee at minimum that responses can be taken seriously. If possible and/or application the procurement should also include all relevant considerations that will be taken into account for the evaluation and the final decision. Typically these include: energy consumption, licensing fees through out the life cycle of the system, services costs throughout the life cycle of the system, targeted life cycle of the system (3 to 5 years as of 2024 for example).

Nowadays, it is also important to provide a baseline targeted architecture (CPU, GPU or APU for example) and if the procurement targets technology watch, and any conditions such as newer architectures (for example as of December 2023 Sapphire Rapids or Mi300). This would affect the timeline for the system, and not all vendors can provide all architectures.

A detailed view of the cluster components should be included. For example:

- Admin and maintenance access,
- Compute centric partition,
- IA centric partition,
- Remote visualization/post-processing partitions with ideally a reference performance for the visualization hardware (example: at least NVIDIA Quadro RTX5000).
- Storage features. Provide a detailed segmentation of the space if applicable and the types (home: NFS, scratch: lustre/gpfs, local node storage: SSD/NVMe). Each store level requires a detailed description of the expected performance and expected usage.
- Login node(s),
- Network characteristics (fat tree, non-blocking, etc ...). These must include any network links to other services already existing in the center (like other computing resources).
- Preferred software environment,
- Specific software (debuggers, scheduler, etc...),
- Preferred network (omnipath, infiniband, sling-shot etc...), topology and target bandwidth.

The desired distribution between compute, IA and visualization nodes should be provided and the integration of the cluster into the existing network detailed. For each partition, minimal requirements if any should be provided. We recommend for example for the compute centric partition to ask for 4GB of RAM per core and for the IA centric partition to include local NVme storage per node.

Beside the technical specifications, the center should provide in the procurement document a detail view of the hosting site with a detailed floor plan and infrastructure capabilities. All physical and technical requirements should be listed. For example, maximum power consumption, current status of the connexion to the power lines, existing cooling systems and requirement to plug in to them, maximum weight per rack.

The official tender schedule should contain the detailed timeline for delivery, testing period and release for production. When building this schedule it is important to consult the HPC vendors to confirm the roadmaps and availability of the architectures. The schedule should give enough time to the benchmarkers to run the procurement cases. Here is a sample schedule for reference for a small to mid size system (in practice the procurement phase should not exceed 12 months) :

- T0: call for propositions to procurement. Procurement is sent to the vendors.
- T0+1: first deadline for vendors to confirm interest and request if any additional information as well as trigger legal considerations (license agreement signatures for access to the data/code for example). This should provide enough time to transfer the code, benchmarks and provide basic support of required by the vendors to run the cases.
- T0+3: Deadline for the first response from vendors.
- T0+4: After analysis of the responses, Confirmation of a short list of candidates.
- T0+5: Final refined proposition from the short list candidates
- T0+6: After analysis, Final decision.

Any legal or payment conditions should be included before hand as well a schedule for the payments.

Finally, the selection criteria for the responses should be included so as to drive the format of the response and avoid out of scope proposals For example :

- Global cost of the solution over 5 years (from january 2023 to December 2028)
- Sustained performance on the provided benchmark and throughput
- Technical quality of the solution and relevance with respect to the targeted requirements.
- Quality of the proposee (re-known, support capabilities, references).

Submission guidelines must be provided. For example a technical and financial proposal should not exceed 50 pages (not counting annexes). Annexes should not be required for the understanding of the proposal. In all cases an electronic copy of the proposal should be submitted. Late submissions will not be considered.

Vendors can be tempted to offset a heavily discounted system with the cost of future optional upgrades. Therefore, it is in the best interest of the party procuring the system to include a maximum cost commitment for upgrades (for example doubling storage, adding future post-processing or data centric nodes).

B.2. Benchmark suite for procurement of the HPC systems

A sample git repository containing a benchmark for WalBerla (OpenSource) is available here : <https://code.it4i.cz/eurohpc-scalable/scalable-benchmarks>. This benchmark includes build instructions for EuroHPC JU systems JUWELS BOOSTER and LUMI G as example with the description of the use cases. Typically, strong and weak scaling up to a target number of nodes should be requested and a clear performance metric and how to measure it must be defined. This git repository is freely downloadable

C. Exploration of the market for future technologies

This part will explore the market for future technologies and identify their potential for SCALABLE codes. We focus only on the description of the hardware that is available and that will be available in the upcoming months and years.

C.1. AMD CPUs

The 4th Generation AMD EPYC™ processors, also known as Zen4 EPYC CPUs, are designed with 12 channels of DDR5 memory per x86 processor. This design helps to reduce memory bottlenecks and improve performance for memory-bound workloads such as SCALABLE codes.

For example, the AMD EPYC™ 9654 processor has a system memory specification of up to 4800MT/s per socket with a memory bandwidth of 460.8 GB/s. This is a significant improvement over previous generations, enabling high-performance and energy-efficient solutions optimized for different computing needs². However, actual memory bandwidth can vary depending on the specific model and configuration³.

The real performance as measured by the system integrators (3) is close to 700GB/s with default BIOS settings and almost 800 GB/s with optimal BIOS setting for dual socket system when running the STREAM benchmark. This is an approximate efficiency 87% compared to the theoretical memory bandwidth. In (3) it is also shown that the maximum memory bandwidth is reached only if at least 12 DIMMs per socket are present in the system. Additional key parameters are shown in Figure 3.

Salient Features	Epyc 7001	Epyc 7002	Epyc 7003	Epyc 9004
Socket	SP3	SP3	SP3+	SP5
Core	Zen 1	Zen 2	Zen 3	Zen 4
Core Process	14 nm	7 nm	7 nm	5 nm
Maximum Cores	32	64	64	96
Package (Cores+I/O)	4	8+1	8+1	12+1
CCX Architecture	4 Cores + 8 MB L2 Cache	4 Cores + 16 MB L2 Cache	8 Cores + 32 MB L2 Cache	8 Cores + 32 MB L2 Cache
L3 Cache	64 MB	256 MB	256 MB	384 MB
Memory	8 Channel DDR4-2666	8 Channel DDR4-3200	8 Channel DDR4-3200	12 Channel DDR5-4800
PCI-Express Lanes Per Socket	128 PCI-E 3.0	128 PCI-E 4.0	128 PCI-E 4.0	128/160 PCI-E 5.0
Security	SME, SEV	SME, SEV	SME, SEV, SNP	SME, SEV, SNP
Thermal Range	120W - 180 W	120W - 280 W	120W - 280 W	200 W - 400 W

Figure 3: Comparison of the four generation of AMD Epyc CPUs based on Zen 1 to 4 architectures.

Source: <https://www.nextplatform.com/2022/11/10/amd-genoa-epyc-server-cpus-take-the-heavyweight-title/>

The company is now gearing up for the release of next-generation CPUs based on Zen 5 microarchitecture by late 2024 (5). These processors, part of the EPYC series, will be marketed under the name Turin, featuring three variants: Turin (Zen 5), Turin-X (Zen 5 with 3D Vertical cache), and Turin dense (Zen 5c, designed for cloud applications).

Zen 5 is anticipated to enhance both performance and energy efficiency compared to Zen 4, boasting a 10-15% increase in instructions per cycle and notable performance per watt improvements. Noteworthy specifications include a 48 kBytes L1 cache (16 kBytes larger than Zen 4), while the L2 and L3 caches will maintain Zen 4 sizes, except for the larger cache in Zen 5 with 3D Vertical (Turin-X) (6, 7). Additionally, Zen 5 introduces support for FP-512 capabilities.

Turin is expected to launch with 128 cores per node, each physical processor supporting two logic units, and a projected thermal design power (TDP) of 500 W. Turin dense will feature even more cores per node (up to 192 cores/node) (7).

For the next generation AMD Epyc CPU based on Zen architecture it is expected that memory performance will be increased from 4800MT/s to at least 6000MT/s resulting in additional 25% performance increase related to memory subsystem. (4)

Looking ahead, the successor to Turin is slated for a 2025 release, based on the Zen 6 architecture, with details currently undisclosed (7).

Source:

- (1) 4th Gen AMD EPYC Processor Architecture. <https://www.amd.com/system/files/documents/4th-gen-epyc-processor-architecture-white-paper.pdf>
- (2) AMD EPYC™ 4th Gen 9004 8004 Series Server Processors – Details. <https://www.amd.com/en/products/processors/server/epyc/4th-generation-9004-and-8004-series.html>
- (3) DDR5 Memory Bandwidth for Next-Generation PowerEdge Servers Featuring <https://infohub.delltechnologies.com/p/ddr5-memory-bandwidth-for-next-generation-poweredge-servers-featuring-4th-gen-amd-epyc-processors/>
- (4) AMD EPYC Turin Zen 5 CPUs Rumored <https://wccftech.com/amd-epyc-turin-zen-5-cpus-rumored-to-feature-up-to-256-cores-192-core-configurations-max-600w-configurable-t-dps/>
- (5) AMD Updated Epyc Roadmap: 5th Gen EPYC “Turin” Announced, Coming by End 2024 <https://www.anandtech.com/show/17437/amd-updated-epyc-roadmap-until-2024-5th-gen-epyc-announced-coming-by-end-of-2024>
- (6) AMD Zen 5 Microarchitecture <https://www.techpowerup.com/314231/amd-zen-5-microarchitecture-referenced-in-leaked-slides>
- (7) AMD Zen 5 Zen 5C EPYC CPU <https://wccftech.com/amd-zen-5-zen-5c-epyc-cpu-turin-16-ccd-128-cores-turin-dense-12-ccd-192-cores-turin-x-1-5-gb-cache/>

C.2. Intel CPUs

The current leading-edge technology for Intel CPU in the realm of High-Performance Computing (HPC) is Sapphire Rapids, which was introduced in January 2023. Following Sapphire Rapids, the next iteration, Emerald Rapids, is expected to be launched at the end of 2023. However, Intel has not yet disclosed whether there will be a commercialized HBM version of Emerald Rapids specifically tailored for HPC (1). Notably, Intel’s public roadmap primarily focuses on general data centers, treating HPC as a subset of this broader category.

The microarchitecture of Emerald Rapids, also identified as Xeon Platinum 8580, introduces the new Raptor Cove core. Featuring support for over 60 cores with 2 threads each, the CPU will operate at a clock frequency of 2000 MHz. The L2 and L3 caches in Emerald Rapids will be 120 MB (consistent with Sapphire Rapids) and 300 MB (2.66 times larger than Sapphire Rapids), respectively. Consequently, these caches will be 87.5% and 17.2% larger than those in AMD EPYC 9554 (Genoa). The anticipated TDP is 350 W, and overall performance-per-watt efficiency is expected to improve compared to Sapphire Rapids. Emerald Rapids will have native support for DDR5-5600, an upgrade from DDR-4800 present in Sapphire Rapids. This enhancement results in a larger memory bandwidth available to the cores. Additionally, the CPU will feature 80 high-speed PCIe 5.0 lanes for rapid connectivity, and support for CXL (2).

Subsequent to Emerald Rapids, Granite Rapids is scheduled for release in 2024. It will mark the first Intel product to support higher bandwidth Multiple Combined Rank (MCR) DIMM memory. In demonstrative tests conducted by Intel on a dual-socket system, Granite Rapids showcased a remarkable 1.5 TB/second of memory bandwidth. Its design will be structured around tiles, featuring separate compute and I/O tiles, a significant departure from Sapphire Rapids, where each tile represents a complete system on a chip. Furthermore, the number of tiles in Granite Rapids is reduced from 4 to 2 (3).

- (1) Intel HPC Updates for ISC 2023 <https://www.anandtech.com/show/18869/intel-hpc-update-isc-2023-falcon-shores-details-future-xpu-aurora-nearly-done>
- (2) 5th-Gen Emerald Rapids CPU Leak Shows 60 Cores, 420MB Cache <https://www.tomshardware.com/news/5th-gen-emerald-rapids-cpu-leak-shows-60-cores-420mb-cache>
- (3) Intel Updates Data Center Roadmap <https://www.anandtech.com/show/18797/intel-updates-data-center-roadmap-xeons-on-track-emerald-in-q423-sierra-forest-in-h124>

C.3. ARM CPUs

There are two key ARM based HW platforms that are interesting and will make significant impact on the European HPC ecosystem. The first is the future Rhea processor developed by the SiPearl company and co-developed by the European Processor Initiative (EPI) project. The second is the NVidia Grace CPU. Its variation with closely coupled Nvidia Hopper GPU (GraceHopper) will be a basic building block of the first European HPC system Jupiter installed in FZJ.

C.3.1. Rhea processor

SiPearl’s first chip, Rhea, will utilize 72 or more ARM Neoverse-V1 cores, each equipped with ARM’s Scalable Vector Extension (SVE) featuring a vector size of 256 bits. From the SCALABLE application point of view, the most important feature of the CPU is the presence of HBM2e memory, positioning it among the fastest options available. It is a similar memory subsystem like the one on Sapphire Rapids with HBM (HBM + DDR5 memories). Additional technical specifications can be explored in Figure 4

In collaboration with the European Processor Initiative, this project will house prototypes of accelerators contributed by various EPI partners.

This initiative is also a key component of the Jupiter Exascale CPU cluster system in Jülich, as revealed in October, and will showcase the inaugural European processor. The anticipated availability of the initial chips is slated for 2024.

Figure 4: SiPearl Rhea Processor characteristics [Image credit: SiPearl]

C.3.2. Grace processor

The NVIDIA Grace has the ability to have both the NVIDIA CPU and GPU on the same package equipped with Arm Neoverse-V2 cores, the NVIDIA Grace Superchip has two 72-core CPUs, integrated memory, and a NVLINK C2C interconnect between them. Key parameters are summarized in Figure 5.

Figure 5: NVIDIA Grace Superchip High-Level Diagram [Image credit: NVidia], (1)

The NVIDIA Grace CPU Superchip integrates up to 960 GB of server-class LPDDR5X memory featuring Error Correction Code (ECC). In comparison, to an eight-channel DDR5 design, the Grace CPU LPDDR5X memory subsystem delivers up to 53% more bandwidth at 1/8th the power per gigabyte per second. Although an HBM2e memory subsystem offers substantial bandwidth and energy efficiency, it comes at more than triple the cost-per-gigabyte with only one-eighth the maximum capacity available in LPDDR5X (1).

The expected STREAM benchmark memory bandwidth based on NVidia simulations presented in architecture whitepaper (1) is approximately 400 GB/s per chip and 800 GB/s per superchip, which is equivalent to a dual-socket x86 server. Grace chip can be equipped with 120, 240 and 480 GB of RAM per chip. The 120 and 240 GB per chip configuration should reach the full bandwidth; however, the large capacity solution will be

penalized in memory bandwidth by approximately 25% (2). This should be taken into account during the procurement.

- (1) NVIDIA Grace CPU Superchip Whitepaper, NVidia, <https://resources.nvidia.com/en-us-grace-cpu/nvidia-grace-cpu-superchip>
- (2) NVIDIA Grace Performance Tuning Guide, NVidia, <https://docs.nvidia.com/grace-performance-tuning-guide.pdf>

C.4. AMD GPU accelerators

The MI250x is AMD instinct GPU released on Nov 8, 2021. It consists of two MI200 Graphics Compute Die (GCD) for the total of 220 compute units resulting in FP64 theoretical performance of 47.9 TFLOPS. This GPU is equipped with 128 GB of HBM2e memory with theoretical throughput of 3.2 TB/s. The energy consumption is around 500W. These GPUs are usually paired with AMD CPUs using AMD's advanced 3D package and chiplet-based construction of CDNA 2 architecture. Using advanced packaging, up to 4 GPUs are present alongside CPUs in a single server. A typical architecture of such server, also used in LUMI-G supercomputer, can be seen in Figure 6. In the figure there are 4 MI250X accelerators effectively acting as 8 distinct GPUs. Each GCD has 8 connections to either other GCDs, CPU or NIC. The two GCDs in the MI250x modules are connected by an in-package Infinity Fabric interface that can provide a theoretical peak bidirectional bandwidth of up to 400 GB/s. Additionally, GCDs on different MI250x modules are linked with either a single or double Infinity Fabric link, which can provide a peak bidirectional bandwidth of 100 GB/s and 200 GB/s, respectively. The connection to CPU and NICs is realized by less performing Infinity Fabric link providing memory coherency capable of 50 GB/s throughput and PCIe Gen4, respectively.

The MI300X is the successor of MI250x released on December 6, 2023. It is based on the new architecture CDNA 3. The MI300X consists of 8 XCD bringing the number of compute units to 304. This results in FP64 performance of 81.7 TFLOPS, a solid 70% increase from previous generation. In terms of memory, the new GPU is equipped with 192 GB of HBM3, the largest capacity of currently available GPUs, with 5.3 TB/s. Both aspects have significance for SCALABLE codes and have been improved by about 30% compared to the previous version. The GPU possesses 7x16 AMD Infinity Fabric links and 1x16 PCIe Gen5 to the host CPU. The power drawn by the GPU is around 750W.

A very promising concept, comparable to NVidia Grace CPU Superchip, is MI300A. Here A stands for APU which is a chip identical to MI300X; however, 2 XCD are replaced by 3 AMD Zen 4 CPU chiplets. In total this chip has 228 compute units and 24 x86 cores. HBM3 memory with capacity of 128 GB is directly accessible from both chiplets and XCDs. This eliminates any need for explicit CPU-GPU memory transfers or coherent interconnect. This has the potential to significantly simplify the programming of accelerators and substantially improve performance not only of LBM applications. The performance of the GPU part was naturally decreased by 25% to 61.3 TFLOPS. The overall capacity of HBM memory also dropped to 128 GB; however, the bandwidth remained the same at 5.3 TB/s. The devices I/O connections are of two forms, either 4x16 Infinity Fabric links and 4x16 PCIe Gen 5 or 8x16 Infinity Fabric links. In a server, up to four APUs can be connected together (see Figure7).

C.5. NVidia GPU accelerators

The A100 PCIe 80 GB is a professional graphics card from NVIDIA, launched on June 28th, 2021. This GPU is capable of achieving 9.7 TFLOPS of FP64 performance. It is equipped with 40 GB of HBM2e with 1.55 TB/s throughput. This GPU is also installed in the Karolina supercomputer of IT4Innovation in Ostrava, Czech Republic. As it is a relatively old GPU, we are not focusing on it in this section.

NVidia H100 GPUs are one of the latest products launched on March 21, 2023. They are based on GH100 graphics processor featuring Hopper microarchitecture. For HPC applications, H100 triples the FLOPS of FP64 and adds dynamic programming (DPX) instructions to deliver up to 7X higher performance when compared with the previous architecture.

The H100 SXM version is capable of attaining 34 TFLOPS of theoretical performance for computation in FP64. This is supported by 80 GB of HBM3 memory with throughput of 3.35 TB/s, which is important for SCALABLE codes(1). A single server can feature up to 8 H100 GPUs. On a server, these GPUs can be interconnected using NVLink. H100 includes 18 fourth-generation NVLink links to provide 900 GB/s total bandwidth, while predecessor A100 includes 12 third-generation NVLink links to provide 600 GB/s total bandwidth(1). This is an increase of 33% in the GPU-to-GPU bandwidth. For other types of communication, H100 incorporates a PCI Express Gen 5 x16 lane interface, providing 128 GB/s total bandwidth.

However, this performance statistic is related only to the SXM form factor. For standard PCI factor, the performance of the card is considerably lower. The PCIe version achieves only 75% of FP64 performance and

Figure 6: Diagram of the AMD MI250X based compute node with single CPU and four physical accelerators. Source: <https://www.amd.com/content/dam/amd/en/documents/instinct-business-docs/white-papers/amd-cdna2-white-paper.pdf>

only 2 TB/s of HBM memory bandwidth. This is more than compensated for by substantial energy savings. The TPD of PCIe form is between 300W and 350W compared to upwards of 700W for SXM.

The servers can be equipped with up to 8 of GPUs of this type interconnected by NVLink with total bandwidth of 600GB/s and using the same PCIe Gen5 with 128GB/s throughput.

NVidia also provides H100 in HVL version. These are two H100 PCIe based cards connected using the NVLink bridge. The FP64 performance of this configuration is 68 TFLOPS (double the H100 SXM performance). In addition, this configuration provides more than double of HBM memory. The overall capacity is 188 GB with a bandwidth of 7.8TB/s. A single server can host only up to 4 GPUs of this type, however, the aggregate theoretical performance of 4-GPU server is significantly better when compared to 8-GPU H100 PCIe server.

NVidia plans to release H200 in the second quarter of 2024. According to specification (3), this GPU will be almost identical to the H100 SXM. The largest improvement will be in terms of memory. The new H200 will feature 141 GB of HBM3e memory at 4.8 TB/s. This represents a 76% increase in capacity and a roughly 41% increase in bandwidth. From the point of view of SCALABLE codes, this product can substantially improve the performance of LBM codes just by virtue of improved bandwidth.

- (1) NVIDIA Grace CPU Superchip Whitepaper, NVidia, <https://resources.nvidia.com/en-us-tensor-core/nvidia-tensor-core-gpu-datasheetp>
- (2) NVIDIA H100 Tensor Core GPU Architecture, NVidia, <https://resources.nvidia.com/en-us-tensor-core>
- (3) NVIDIA H200 Tensor Core GPU, <https://nvdam.widen.net/s/nb5zzzsjdf/hpc-datasheet-sc23-h200-datasheet-3002446>

Figure 7: Diagram of the compute node based on four MI300A APUs.

Source: <https://www.amd.com/content/dam/amd/en/documents/instinct-tech-docs/white-papers/amd-cdna-3-white-paper.pdf>

C.6. Intel GPU accelerators

The latest addition to the Intel GPU product line is the Intel Data Center GPU Max series, previously code named Ponte Vecchio, which is designed to take on high-performance computing and AI workloads. In context of SCALABLE, two relevant products were launched in year 2023, namely Intel GPU Max 1550 and scaled down Max 1100. The former is a Xe-HPC data center GPU possessing 128 Xe-cores, 128 ray tracing units, 8 hardware contexts, 8 HBM2e controllers, and 16 Xe-Links. With each core capable of 128 FP64 operations/cycle, this totals to 16384 FP64 operations/cycle of theoretical performance or 14.745 and 26.214 FP64 TFLOP/s using 900 MHz nominal and 1600 MHz max dynamic frequency, respectively. With 8 HBM2e controllers, this GPU provides 3276.8 GB/s of theoretical throughput and 128 GB of combined capacity. All this comes with a TDP of 500W.

A scale-down version, Max 1100, has 56 Xe-cores resulting in overall peak performance of 11.110 FP64 TFLOP/s. However, for less than half the performance of the full-scale version, the TDP is relatively high, sitting at 300W.

Accelerator form factor	Memory	TDP	Peak Performance double	PCIe generation
NVidia A100 SXM	40 GB HBM2e 1.55 TB/s	400W	9.78 TFLOPS	4.0 x16 64 GB/s
AMD MI250X OAM	128 GB HBM2e 3.2 TB/s	500W 560W peak	47.9 TFLOPS	4.0 x16 64 GB/s
NVidia H100 SXM	80 GB HBM3 3.4 TB/s	700W	34 TFLOPS	5.0 x16 128 GB/s
AMD MI300X OAM	192 GB HBM3 5.3 TB/s	750W peak	81.7 TFLOPS	5.0 X16 128 GB/s
AMD MI300A APU SH5 Socket	128 GB HBM3 5.3 TB/s	550W 760W peak	61.3 TFLOPS +24 CPU cores Zen4	128 GB/s
Intel Max 1550 PCIe	128 GB HBM2e 3.2 TB/s	500W	26.2 TFLOPS	5.0 X16 128 GB/s
Intel Max 1100 PCIe	48 GB HBM2e 1.2 TB/s	300W	11.110 TFLOPS	5.0 X16 128 GB/s

Table 10: Comparison of the basic parameters for current and future HPC GPU and APU accelerators.

References

- [1] John D. McCalpin. “Bandwidth Limits in the Intel Xeon Max (Sapphire Rapids with HBM) Processors.” In: *High Performance Computing - ISC High Performance 2023 International Workshops, Hamburg, Germany, May 21-25, 2023, Revised Selected Papers*. Ed. by Amanda Bienz et al. Vol. 13999. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2023, pp. 403–413. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-031-40843-4_30](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-40843-4_30). URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-40843-4_30.

